
COMMUNICATION, DISSEMINATION AND EXPLOITATION PLAN

General information

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Version n°	Date	Description	Authors
V1.0	03/03/23	First version	Imen Ben Mahmoud
V2.0	09/01/24	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• The elements in section 2 are mostly drafted from information available in the Grant agreement and go through the EU requirements and the guidelines for publication of results.• Section 3 contains information from the original Deliverable, with additions on new parts: key messages, communication channels and the timeline of activities.• Section 4 and 5 present new brand elements and new brand guidelines, the external communication strategy, and the organizational workflow of internal and external strategies.• Section 6 is an updated table of KPIs	Daniele Baldo

Executive Summary

This deliverable aims to develop a common communication strategy and to create common communication tools for the project. It revolves around **developing** and **implementing** an **effective** and **efficient** communication to build a strong internal and external communication network and to promote the services offered by the AgroServ consortium. It will play a strategic role in the AgroServ project as it has for main objectives the following:

1. **To support** different WPs in their communication needs and tools.
2. **To attract** users by promoting the service offer and increasing the visibility of the project and the associated research infrastructures.
3. **To promote** scientific results among the research community and support the development of the agroecology community.
4. **To provide** content for evidence-based policy making to support sustainable and resilient agriculture, and agroecological transitions.

Communication support to other WPs

Layout & publications (digital / print)

- Protocols & guidelines, reports & plans, toolkits

Digital presence

- E-platforms, access portals, data portals, catalogue of services, knowledge hubs, publications of calls

Event organization

- Meetings, training sessions, workshops, conferences

This document constitutes the first deliverable in the communication work package:

Number	Deliverable name	Communication	Month
D8.1	Communication plan	360° strategy	3
D8.2	Digital identity, website & social media	Digital	9
D8.3	Synthesis for policy makers	Print / Digital	36
D8.4	2nd Synthesis for policy makers	Print / Digital	56
D8.5	Final report on outreach & dissemination activities	Print / Digital	56
30	AgroServ conference (1)	Event/Kick-off	10
33	AgroServ conference (2)	Event	36
36	AgroServ conference (3)	Event/Closing	58
31	Thematic webinar (1)	Event (online)	20
32	Thematic webinar (2)	Event (online)	30
34	Thematic webinar (3)	Event (online)	40
35	Thematic webinar (4)	Event (online)	50

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1. Scope and purpose of the document

1.1. General overview

A communication strategy, for a project, is the overall framework that defines the key messages and the methodology behind communicating about a project. It needs to be mapped prior to setting out operational communication plans that focus on target groups and dissemination tools and channels.

If the communication strategy is the guiding ambition behind communicating effectively and efficiently about the AgroServ project, the communication plans (internal, external) are the set of actions one needs to undertake to translate that ambition into viable and concrete results.

Communicating about AgroServ

Figure 1: communicating about AgroServ

In the context of AgroServ, which is a Horizon Europe funded project, the communication plans are the means to implement the strategy adopted. They need to be based on tangible, measurable and verifiable objectives. They have a threefold purpose:

1. Promoting the project actions and results (communication)

2. Making the project results public (dissemination)
1. Making concrete use of results (exploitation)¹

The difference between “communication”, “dissemination” and “exploitation” (often included under the umbrella terms of “communications” – plural form – or “outreach”) is important in the sense that they all constitute mandatory activities for Horizon Europe projects and are a central constituent of the measures to maximise “impact” for the AgroServ project.

1.2. Purpose and organisation

The aim of this document is to:

1. outline the strategy for communication, dissemination and exploitation regarding activities carried out during the AgroServ project
2. present the different communication actions that will be launched to meet the project’s objectives for an internal and external audience (additional goals and activities may emerge along the way based on the audience or focus groups that the project aims to reach).

This document is structured in four main sections addressing the different aspects that a communications roadmap may focus on:

1. Context & key challenges
2. Strategy & methodology
3. Organisation & implementation
4. Evaluation & monitoring

1.3. The case of communicating about a scientific project

When communicating about AgroServ’s scientific services and results, it is important to examine the diverse local and regional contexts in which the project will be operating to ensure an effective communication of the messages towards the different target groups of the project.

¹ Horizon Europe: dissemination and exploitation resources
https://rea.ec.europa.eu/dissemination-and-exploitation_en

General, and science, communications approaches will be put into practice and will be adapted to “inform, engage, persuade, change behaviours and support better decision making”².

Based on the acquired knowledge about the actual context, communication priorities will be set on the topics the project will want to engage with first, and this based on the needs and expectations of the community and on the public understanding of certain subjects.

Communication efforts will in this sense be oriented toward better understanding the public perceptions of emerging fields like “agroecology”, the capacity of science to inform policy and decision-making, and the importance of continuing to monitor the communication impact metrics to measure the success of the project’s communication activities and to adapt them when necessary.

Engaging in a constructive dialogue with the different stakeholders (internal and external) will prove to be fruitful and efficient to communicate about the services offered and will eventually pave the way to boosting the practices of co-creation and open innovation that the project aims to consolidate through a transdisciplinary and a multi-actor approach (“Living Labs”, etc.).

For communication purposes, the project will pay attention to “who reads?”, “who follows?”, “who interacts?” and “who might be interested in collaborating?” to offer a response tailored to the local and regional needs of its large community (current and potential).

A rethinking and adoption of new communication practices (online & in-person) will be thoroughly investigated to communicate about the innovative ways of doing science that the project aims to achieve through engaging in creative communication and storytelling.

The work on the communication package will be conducted through the lens of encouraging interdisciplinary and transdisciplinary approaches³, while paying close attention to the digital literacy of the target audience and to the scientific debate on related subjects that is increasingly popularised by/on social media.

² Gascoigne, T., Schiele, B., Leach, J., Riedlinger, M., Lewenstein, B. V., Massarani, L.; Broks, P. *Communicating science: A global perspective* (Australian National University Press, 2020).

³ See AgroServ’s [Deliverable 2.1 – Catalogue of services](#)

2. Guidelines for Communication and Dissemination Activities

This document is intended to provide a clear and comprehensive approach of the dissemination activities to be implemented during the project, as well as to provide project partners with guidance and rules to ensure a well-defined and homogeneous communication.

The dissemination activities will address the AgroServ target groups. A wide range of stakeholders will be addressed through a wide range of dissemination tools and channels.

A coherent, multi-layered strategy to effectively publicise and exploit AgroServ's outputs will bundle input from the whole consortium across the entire lifespan of the project. Effective dissemination, communication and exploitation of findings are central to successful high impact whenever the project involves multiple groups of academic and non-academic partners and audiences.

The dissemination and communication process will focus on:

- Disseminating the specific results and insights of the project
- Communicating about the project's broader activities

A central goal of communication and dissemination is to maximise opportunities to promote, communicate and disseminate results throughout the lifetime of the project, and beyond. This will ensure that key stakeholders can contribute to, and act on the findings in a timely fashion.

Dissemination, communication and exploitation activities pursue different objectives.

The main objectives of WP8 are to define communication and dissemination activities to be carried out throughout (and for a limited time afterwards) the project to ensure that results will effectively benefit as many EU citizens as possible. The WP8 team will continuously monitor and provide means for the AgroServ partners to share results within the consortium and to integrate research and innovation (R&I) activities, as well as to communicate developments, disseminate results to the industrial and scientific community and to a broad stakeholder audience, to encourage the use and wide acceptance of the project's output.

Specific objectives:

- To establish the internal procedures to disseminate the project results to external stakeholders.
- To prepare the visual identity and a set of materials for the promotion of the AgroServ project.
- To carry out engagement and interaction activities with key external stakeholders.
- To enable a showcase of the project at conferences and events for dissemination purposes

2.1 European Commission rules as established in the GA

The AgroServ project, as a beneficiary of European Union funding, must adhere to comprehensive communication, dissemination, and visibility requirements as outlined in Article 17 of the Grant Agreement:

1. Communication and Dissemination (**article 17.1**): AgroServ must promote its action and results to multiple audiences, including the media and public, in a strategic, coherent, and effective manner. Before engaging in communication activities expected to have major media impact, AgroServ must inform the granting authority.
2. Visibility - European Flag and Funding Statement (**article 17.2**): All communication activities, dissemination materials, and funded items (including infrastructure, equipment, and major results) must display the European flag (emblem) and a funding statement. The emblem must remain distinct, unmodified, and as prominent as other logos. AgroServ can use the emblem without prior approval but doesn't have exclusive rights to it.
3. Quality of Information and Disclaimer (**article 17.3**): All communicated information must be factually accurate. A specific disclaimer must be included, stating that the views expressed are those of the authors and do not necessarily reflect those of the EU or the granting authority.

Dissemination requirements also involve beneficiaries of the AgroServ project.

According to **Annex 5** of the Grant Agreement, beneficiaries must disseminate their results as soon as feasible. Annex 5 also states that AgroServ must ensure open access to peer-reviewed scientific publications by depositing them in trusted repositories, providing immediate open

access, and using appropriate Creative Commons licenses. Metadata must be open under CC 0 or equivalent. AgroServ must manage digital research data responsibly, following FAIR principles ('findability', 'accessibility', 'interoperability' and 'reusability'). This includes establishing a data management plan, depositing data in trusted repositories, ensuring open access to data (with exceptions for legitimate interests), and providing open metadata.

Furthermore, beneficiaries must comply with any additional open scientific obligations specified in the call conditions. This may include providing access to data for validation of scientific publications and, in case of public emergencies, immediately depositing and providing open access to research outputs.

Further information on publication requirements and data management are detailed in AgroServ's [Deliverable 9.4 – Project Data Management Plan](#).

2.2 The role of Consortium Partners

Figure 2: The AgroServ Consortium

AgroServ gathers 73 partners of Beneficiaries, Affiliated entities and Associated Partners.

This diverse group represents a high impact potential for dissemination and communication activities. All partners are expected to actively contribute to these efforts, leveraging their existing resources and networks.

Key responsibilities of consortium partners include:

1. Dissemination through existing channels
 - a. Utilise institutional websites, newsletters, and social media accounts
 - b. Share AgroServ news and updates through their networks
 - c. Translate key materials into local languages when appropriate
2. Participation in scientific events
 - a. Present and represent AgroServ at relevant conferences, workshops, and seminars
 - b. Acknowledge AgroServ support (and EU support as detailed in section 2.1) when presenting results from using the services
 - c. Seek opportunities to organise AgroServ-specific sessions at major events
3. Content creation
 - a. Contribute regular updates on their AgroServ-related activities
 - b. Provide case studies and success stories from their work
 - c. Assist in creating technical content for various audiences
4. Stakeholder engagement
 - a. Identify and engage with relevant stakeholders in their regions
 - b. Organize local dissemination activities, such as information days or workshops
 - c. Facilitate connections between AgroServ and potential users and collaborators
5. Reporting and monitoring
 - a. Regularly report on dissemination activities
 - b. Track and share metrics on the reach and impact of their efforts

To coordinate these efforts, a Communication Board⁴ will be established, comprising communication representatives from each of the 11 research infrastructures in the consortium. This board will meet regularly to align strategies, share best practices, and ensure coherent messaging across the project.

A dedicated Public Relations and Communication Manager⁵ will be hired to oversee all communication activities and coordinate communication activities across the consortium. Their responsibilities will include:

- Developing and implementing the overall communication strategy
- Coordinating with the Communication Board and all partners
- Managing central communication channels (website, social media, newsletters)
- Ensuring compliance with EU requirements and AgroServ branding guidelines
- Organizing project-wide events and coordinating participation in external events

By leveraging the diverse expertise and networks of all consortium partners, AgroServ aims to maximize its reach and impact across various stakeholder groups, from the scientific community to policymakers and the general public.

2.3. Publication Policy and Strategy Rules

AgroServ's publication policy is designed to maximize the dissemination of project results while ensuring compliance with EU regulations. The following rules and strategies will guide all publication activities:

Dissemination of Results from AgroServ Calls:

- Users who gain access to AgroServ facilities through calls will be required to submit a brief report on their research outcomes.

⁴ A working document with updated Communication Board members from consortium partners is available: <https://cloud.agroserv.eu/s/S2BcCW7QGx5Dbs2>

⁵ This position was covered by Imen Ben Mahmoud (project start-October 2023), Amanda Ölander (November 2023-February 2024), Daniele Baldo (March 2024-ongoing).

- These reports will be used to create case studies and success stories, highlighting the impact of AgroServ's services.
- Users will be encouraged to present their results at AgroServ conferences and webinars.
- A dedicated section of the AgroServ website will highlight these research outcomes, providing visibility to the users and demonstrating the value of the infrastructure.
- AgroServ will actively promote these results through its social media channels and newsletters.
- Annual compilations of research highlights will be produced and distributed to stakeholders.

Scientific Publications (see section 2.1):

- Primary scientific publications will come from users of AgroServ services. These users will be required to acknowledge the support of the AgroServ project, and RI facilities and data in their publications.
- All scientific publications must be made available through open access, in compliance with Horizon Europe requirements.

Policy-oriented Publications:

- AgroServ will produce two key policy documents:
 - o A Synthesis Note (D8.3) midway through the project
 - o A Final Note (D8.4) at the project's conclusion
- These documents will target policymakers at European, national, and regional levels, informing them about sustainable agriculture practices and achievements.
- The project aims to contribute to ERIC-Forum policy briefs and activities of Life-Science RIs.

Quality Control:

- An internal review process will be established for all AgroServ-produced publications to ensure high quality and consistency of messaging, which will include coordination with the Executive Committee (as detailed in article 6.3.2.3.5. of the Consortium Agreement).
- The Communication Manager will oversee this process, coordinating with relevant experts within the consortium as needed.

Tracking and Reporting:

- All publications will be logged in a central database, including metadata such as authors, title, journal, date, and acknowledgements.

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- Partners will report their publications in their regular Work Packages activity reports.

By adhering to these rules and strategies, AgroServ aims to contribute significantly to the scientific discourse on agroecology and sustainable agriculture, while also informing policy development in these crucial areas and showcasing the value of its infrastructures' services.

3. Communication and Dissemination Strategy and Plan

The AgroServ communication and dissemination strategy is built upon a careful analysis of the project's Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, and Threats (SWOT). This approach ensures that the strategy is tailored to maximize impact while addressing potential challenges.

Strengths	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ A diverse network to be developed ▪ A unique European programme focused on agroecology ▪ A high level of awareness and recognition of the importance of research in this sector: the demand for agroecology-related services has become a new objective defined in various EU strategies.
Weaknesses	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Considerable number of actors (infrastructures and partners) with diverse types and levels of practices in communication.
Opportunities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Communicate the potential of the agroecological related sectors and highlight their added value ▪ Promote successful projects and improve the exchange of best practices between different stakeholders.
Threats	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Mobility restrictions due to health emergencies ▪ Waning attention granted to agroecology depending on the geopolitical context. ▪ Partner disengagement – at a large scale

Table 1: SWOT analysis on AgroServ's communication activities

By addressing these factors, our communication and dissemination strategy aims to effectively promote AgroServ's services, engage with key stakeholders, and contribute to the advancement of agroecology in Europe. The following sections detail our approach to achieving these goals.

3.1. Target Audience

AgroServ has identified several strategic target groups to achieve the expected outcomes defined in our project objectives. A further analysis of potential stakeholders to be addressed will be detailed by Work Package 5 (D5.3).

Communication and dissemination actions and initiatives will be tailored to address the specific needs and interests of each group:

1. Scientific Community

The primary target within this group includes clusters ENVRI and LSRI, other ongoing RIs, and natural and social-sciences communities involved in agronomy, biodiversity, and environment. We will engage this audience through publications in high-impact, international peer-reviewed journals, presentations at specialized scientific conferences, and organization of thematic webinars. Facilitating access to AgroServ services for research projects will be a key strategy to foster collaboration and knowledge exchange within this community.

2. Agriculture Stakeholders

This group encompasses European and National representing groups of farmers (e.g., COPA-COGECA, ELO, IFOAM Organics Europe), agriculture and food industry representatives, technical organizations (e.g., ENOLL), and National breeders and farmers associations. The engagement strategy will focus on participation in agriculture-related fairs and events, organizing workshops and demonstrations of AgroServ services, and developing case studies that showcase the practical applications of research. We will also leverage the project's Living Labs activities (WP6) to ensure direct engagement with this crucial stakeholder group.

3. Policy makers & society

At the EU level, we will target DG Agri, DG Environment, SCAR, and relevant Working groups in the European Parliament. At the national level, the focus will be on EU ministries of agriculture and environment, local and regional authorities, and think tanks. This approach will involve producing policy synthesis papers, participating in policy-focused events and working groups, organizing targeted briefings, and contributing to ERIC-Forum policy briefs. These efforts aim to support evidence-based policy making in the field of agroecology.

4. Industry

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Industry targets include the agri-food sector, technology providers, and SMEs in the agricultural sector. We will engage this group through participation in industry-focused events like the Smart Agrifood Summit, leveraging industry boards of participating RIs, and developing industry-focused case studies and white papers. Involvement in activities developed under the ENRIITC (European Network of Research Infrastructures and Industry for Collaboration) project will further strengthen industry engagement.

5. General Public

To reach European citizens interested in sustainable agriculture and food production, easily understandable content for the project website will be developed, creating infographics and videos explaining agroecology concepts, and participating in public events. Social media engagement with relatable content on sustainable agriculture will be a key strategy for this audience.

6. Media

We will target both specialized agricultural and scientific media, as well as mainstream news outlets. The media strategy will include issuing regular press releases on project milestones and achievements, offering expert interviews on agroecology topics, and organizing media visits to AgroServ facilities and demonstrations.

3.2. Strategic Approach

The communication strategy is based on the conclusions of the RI-VIS project⁶ on communication for Research Infrastructures. We have developed a multi-faceted approach to ensure maximum impact and reach for AgroServ. The main objectives are:

1. Increase the visibility of AgroServ

As part of Work Package 8 responsibilities, communication materials and online campaigns will strive to increase the visibility of the project. As anticipated in section 2.2 of this document, this will be also achieved by leveraging our diverse network of 73 partners and their existing communication channels. Each partner will be encouraged to

⁶ <https://toolkit.ri-vis.eu/>

promote AgroServ through their institutional websites, social media accounts, and professional networks.

2. Promote events, services, and calls

We will create a comprehensive calendar of events, including our three main conferences (kick-off, mid-term, and closing), four thematic webinars, and various workshops. These events will be widely publicised through multiple channels.

3. Generate traffic to our website to promote services and projects:

The website will serve as the central hub for all AgroServ information. We will regularly update it with news, upcoming calls, and results from research projects.

4. Increase networking partners and prospective users:

We will actively engage with related H2020/HE projects, as well as potential fundamental science projects. Direct contact with coordinators of newly funded and pre-existing projects will be made to propose our catalogue of services.

5. Increase user engagement (establish dialogue):

Considering the objectives of Work Package 5, we will use interactive platforms and social media to encourage two-way communication with stakeholders. Regular surveys and feedback mechanisms will be implemented to ensure we are meeting user needs.

6. Promote the results and outputs of the access to facilities, services or resources:

We will create case studies and success stories from the research conducted using AgroServ services. These will be disseminated through the website, social media, and at relevant conferences and events.

To implement this strategy effectively, we will:

- Hire a dedicated Public Relations and Communication Manager to oversee all communication activities.
- Establish a Communication Board with representatives from each of the 11 research infrastructures to ensure coordinated effort.
- Develop a communication kit, easily exploitable and translated into several European languages, for use at national mainstream fairs and events.
- Allocate a specific budget for advertising the catalogue and upcoming calls through various proxies (scientific societies, involved institutions, related initiatives).

- Leverage the existing communication initiatives of all participating RIs, potentially reaching an initial audience of approximately 120,000 followers⁷.

The strategy will be adaptive, with regular reviews and adjustments based on the effectiveness of activities and any changes in the external environment. This approach will ensure that AgroServ remains visible, accessible, and engage with stakeholders throughout the project's lifetime and beyond.

3.3. Key Messages

AgroServ's key messages are designed to effectively communicate the project's core objectives, values, and expected impacts to the identified target audiences. These messages will be consistently used across all our communication channels and activities:

1. Advancing agroecology research: AgroServ is a unique European programme exclusively focused on agroecology, providing integrated services to support a sustainable agroecological transition. We offer researchers access to state-of-the-art facilities and resources to advance our understanding of the opportunities and challenges agriculture is facing.

2. Transdisciplinary approach: the project brings together a diverse network of 73 partners, offering a transdisciplinary portfolio of services. This approach bridges different research communities and enables holistic solutions to complex agricultural challenges.

3. Supporting sustainable agriculture: AgroServ contributes to the implementation of resilient and sustainable agri-food systems. Our research services assist in reaching goals to enhance biodiversity, reduce greenhouse gas emissions, and improve food quality while ensuring economic sustainability for farmers.

4. Informing policy: we provide evidence-based insights to support policy-making at European, national, and regional levels. Our research outcomes and policy briefs contribute to the effective implementation of the European Green Deal objectives and Sustainable Development Goals.

⁷ As of October 2024, the actual audience subscribed to AgroServ's social media and newsletter counts over 3000 subscribers.

5. Fostering innovation: AgroServ facilitates the development of new technologies and practices in areas such as pest management, smart agriculture, and sustainable food production systems. We support SMEs and industry partners in creating innovative solutions for the agricultural sector.

6. Open Science and collaboration: the project promotes open access to research results and data, fostering collaboration and knowledge exchange across the agroecology community. Our Catalogue of services is designed to expand a wide community of users in agroecology research.

7. Societal impact: AgroServ's work directly contributes to address critical societal challenges related to food security, climate change, and environmental protection. We engage with stakeholders, including farmers and the general public, to ensure our research has real-world applications and benefits.

These key messages will be adapted and refined for each target audience, ensuring that our communication is relevant, impactful, and aligned with the interests and needs of each group. They will be regularly reviewed and updated as the project progresses and results emerge, maintaining their relevance throughout the project's lifetime.

3.4. Communication channels and activities

AgroServ will utilize a diverse range of communication channels and activities to reach target audiences effectively. The approach combines digital platforms, traditional media, and in-person events to ensure comprehensive coverage:

1. Project website

The AgroServ website will serve as the main hub for project information. It will feature news, upcoming TNA calls, metadata, public data, and publications resulting from the projects. The website will be designed to facilitate access to information for external users and internal communication within the consortium. Regular updates will ensure fresh, relevant content.

2. Social media

We will establish and maintain active profiles on platforms such as [X \(Twitter\)](#) and [LinkedIn](#). These channels will be used to share project updates, promote events, and

engage with our community. Existing social media accounts of participating RIs will also be leveraged, potentially reaching an initial audience of approximately 120,000 followers.

3. **Scientific publications**

AgroServ will encourage and support the publication of research results in high-impact, international peer-reviewed journals. We will also produce synthesis notes and reviews for the academic community.

4. **Conferences and workshops**

We will organize three main AgroServ conferences:

- A kick-off conference (M10) organized by CZU
- A mid-term conference (M36) organized by VMU
- A closing conference (M58) organized by AnaEE-ERIC

Additionally, we will participate in major external conferences and events relevant to agroecology and sustainable agriculture.

5. **Webinars**

Four thematic webinars will be organized (M20, M30, M40, M50) to interact with different science communities, train users, and disseminate project results.

6. **Policy Briefs and reports**

Two key policy documents will be produced:

- A Synthesis Note (D8.3) midway through the project
- A Final Note (D8.4) at the project's conclusion

These will target policymakers at European, national, and regional levels.

7. **Newsletter**

A regular e-newsletter will be distributed to keep stakeholders informed about project progress, upcoming events, and key findings.

8. **Press releases and media engagement**

Regular press releases will be issued to coincide with significant project milestones. We will also seek opportunities for media interviews and coverage in both specialized and mainstream outlets.

9. **Participation in public events**

AgroServ will have a presence at public events such as agriculture fairs (e.g., FIMA Zaragoza, Salon de l'Agriculture) and the EU Green Week to engage with a broader audience.

10. **Communication Kit**

We will develop a comprehensive communication kit, easily adaptable and translatable, for use at various events and by all partners.

11. **Living Labs**

Activities in the project's Living Labs (WP6) will provide opportunities for direct engagement with farmers and local stakeholders.

Through these diverse channels and activities, AgroServ aims to maintain consistent and effective communication with all target audiences throughout the project's duration. Our approach will be flexible, allowing for adjustments based on feedback and the evolving needs of our stakeholders.

3.5. Timeline of activities

The AgroServ communication and dissemination activities will be implemented throughout the project's 60-month duration (2022-2027). The timeline is designed to align with key project milestones and maximize impact. See Appendix 4 for a GANTT view of the activities.

Year 1 (2022- 2023)	Awareness	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Launch website and social media channels - Develop and distribute initial communication kit - Kick-off conference (M10) - First thematic webinar (M20) - Initiate regular newsletter distribution
Year 2 (2023- 2024)	Engagement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Continue social media engagement and website updates - Second thematic webinar (M30) - Participate in external conferences and events - First round of training workshops - Publish initial research results and case studies
Year 3 (2024- 2025)	Mid-term intensification	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Publish Synthesis Note for policymakers (D8.3) - Mid-term conference (M36) - Third thematic webinar (M40) - Increase policy engagement activities - Second round of training workshops
Year 4 (2025- 2026)	Results dissemination	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Continue publishing research results - Fourth thematic webinar (M50) - Participate in major international conferences - Intensify media engagement - Third round of training workshops
Year 5 (2026- 2027)	Legacy and impact	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Closing conference (M58) - Publish Final Note for policymakers (D8.4) - Compile and disseminate success stories and case studies - Develop sustainability plan for future activities - Final round of training workshops

Table 2: overview of the planned activities

Throughout the project's duration, a series of continuous activities will be implemented to maintain engagement and disseminate information. These activities encompass regular updates to the project's digital platforms, including the website and social media channels, to ensure a consistent flow of information to stakeholders. A key component of these updates will be the advertisement of open calls for access to AgroServ services, ensuring wide dissemination to potential users. The consortium will maintain a continuous output of scientific publications and policy briefs, thereby contributing to the expansion of knowledge in the field of agroecology and informing policy decisions. Stakeholder engagement will be sustained through ongoing Living Labs activities (in WP6), which will foster collaboration and facilitate the practical application of research findings. Furthermore, the communication strategy will undergo periodic evaluation and adjustments to ensure its continued effectiveness and adaptability to emerging needs and opportunities within the project's ecosystem.

3.6. Evaluation and Monitoring

Evaluation and monitoring are integral components of AgroServ's communication strategy, ensuring the effectiveness of dissemination actions and allowing for timely adjustments.

Monitoring is an ongoing process that systematically tracks our communication activities and their immediate output. It involves the continuous collection of data on predefined indicators, providing real-time insights into the implementation of our communication strategy. This includes tracking metrics such as website traffic, social media engagement, publication downloads, and event attendance. Monitoring will be conducted on a regular basis, with data collected and reviewed monthly by the communication team.

Evaluation, on the other hand, is a periodic assessment of the overall effectiveness, impact, and sustainability of the communication efforts. It goes beyond tracking output to analyse outcomes and long-term impacts. Evaluations will be conducted at every reporting period, aligning with the project's overall reporting structure. These assessments will examine the extent to which communication activities are contributing to the project's broader objectives, stakeholder engagement, and the advancement of agroecology in Europe.

Both monitoring and evaluation are crucial as they allow us to measure progress towards our objectives, provide insights into the effectiveness of different channels and messages, help identify areas for improvement, and demonstrate the value and impact of our activities to stakeholders.

The approach to monitoring and evaluation is based on several key principles. It will be comprehensive, covering all aspects of our communication strategy. We are committed to a data-driven approach, basing decisions and adjustments on both quantitative and qualitative data. **Flexibility** is also key: evaluation methods will adapt to changing project needs and emerging communication trends.

The evaluation process will be subject to regular **oversight and feedback** from key project governance structures. The Communication Board (WP8), comprising communication representatives from each of the 11 research infrastructures, will regularly provide feedback and recommendations for strategy adjustments. Additionally, the project's Executive Committee will provide feedback and review main activities, ensuring that communication activities align with overall project objectives and governance.

Successful approaches will be reinforced and potentially expanded, while underperforming activities will be analysed and either improved or phased out. New opportunities identified through the evaluation process will be incorporated into the strategy, and recommendations from the governance bodies will be integrated into strategic planning.

By maintaining this strategic approach to evaluation and monitoring, with robust oversight from key project structures, we ensure that communication efforts remain aligned with project goals, stakeholder needs, and best practices in scientific communication. Detailed Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) and specific evaluation methodologies will be outlined in Section 6 of this document.

4. Project Identity Set and Dissemination Tools

This section outlines AgroServ's visual identity and key dissemination tools. Our project identity set includes the logo, colour scheme, typography, and style, ensuring consistent and recognizable communication across all channels. The dissemination tools comprise various materials and platforms we'll use to promote AgroServ, including templates, leaflets, our website, videos, and social media channels. These elements form the foundation of the communication strategy, enabling us to present AgroServ professionally and cohesively to all stakeholders across both traditional and digital platforms.

4.1. Brand Guidelines

Brand guidelines provide the established official policies and standards for AgroServ's visual identity. They are applied to all materials, whether print or digital. They include updated guidelines⁸ on the proper use of the logo, colours, fonts, and official messaging. Brand guidelines ensure that all marketing and internal and external communications are accurate and stay on-brand, to get a coherent and professional messaging across-the-board.

4.1.1. Overview of existing branding elements

Logo: *the main logo, minimal version, and variations for different backgrounds*

A logo is the visual representation of a project. AgroServ's logo symbolizes the partnership and trans-disciplinary values embodied by the 11 Research Infrastructures, striving for a sustainable future for living beings and society as a whole, working within the agroecology field. It can be used on all print media, all advertising platforms, websites, and other internal and external communications.

⁸ The first visual identity document is available here: <https://cloud.agroserv.eu/f/5622>

Figure 3: AgroServ official logo

Figure 4: AgroServ minimal logo

For dark background usage, an alternate logo is also available for both the original and minimal versions.

Figure 5: AgroServ white logo

Colour Palette: primary and secondary colour schemes with CMYK and RGB values

Figure 6: AgroServ colour palettes

Typography: Titillium Web and Montserrat as main fonts, with fallback options

The main font is Titillium Web, a recognisable open-source typeface very common in EU related projects. Alongside it Montserrat, another open source font used for headings.

Figure 7: AgroServ typefaces

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Communication Kit and Templates

On [AgroServ's cloud](#) platform it is possible to find the latest version⁹ of several templates (simple Word document, PowerPoint, Deliverables) as well as the Communication Kit (logos, promotional materials, boilerplates).

4.1.2. Application in AgroServ Communications

Logo Usage:

The logo will be used prominently in all visual communications, following the placement and size guidelines provided. The logo should be used on light or dark backgrounds avoiding strong accent colors. When this is not possible, or when printing in black and white, a specific monochrome logo alternate is available. The main logo comes with a minimal version, which must be used in case the usage prevents readability of the baseline.

Minimum sizes of the logo should be 150px for digital usage and 22mm for print materials. The logo should not be placed with another graphic or edited to create a new image. For legibility, the area around the logo should be clear. The logo's colours cannot be changed or modified.

In all public documents the logo must be accompanied by the EU logo "Funded by the European Union".

⁹ With this second version of the deliverable, Brand Guidelines have been drafted to adhere with the already existing visual identity built on AgroServ's logo. New templates and guidelines are now homogeneous and aim to expand the brand identity and recognizability of the project.

Figure 8: logo usage and EU institutional logo usage examples

Colour Application:

The defined colour palette will be used for design elements, text, and backgrounds as specified.

Figure 9: colour schemes for branded materials

4.2. Digital Presence

AgroServ's digital presence is crucial for reaching and engaging with our diverse stakeholders. Our primary digital platforms will be our project website and social media channels.

4.2.1. Website

The AgroServ website (agroserv.eu) serves as the main hub for project information and updates.

Key features and content include:

- [Project overview and objectives](#)
- [Partner information](#)
- [News and events](#)
- Access to the [Catalogue of Services](#)
- [Publications and resources](#)
- [Contact information](#)

Additional key elements:

- [Newsletter archive](#)
- [Public deliverables repository](#)
- [Detailed information on TA/VA calls and application guidelines](#)
- Stakeholder engagement strategy (WP5) section
- [Knowledge Hub for Data Management \(WP3\)](#)
- Living Labs (WP6) space detailing activities with farmers and industry experts

The website will be regularly updated to ensure fresh, relevant content. It will be designed to be user-friendly, responsive, and accessible across different devices.

4.2.2. Social Media

To complement our website and reach a broader audience, AgroServ will maintain an active presence on key social media platforms:

- **LinkedIn and X (Twitter):**
 - Bi-weekly posts with flexible schedules based on project needs
 - Content tailored to different audience segments to expand reach and awareness
 - Leveraging the consortium's wide network for extensive post diffusion
- **YouTube:**
 - Hosting webinar recordings
 - Sharing promotional videos created within WP8

The social media strategy will focus on:

- Maintaining a regular posting schedule to ensure consistent engagement
- Sharing project milestones, events, and open calls
- Highlighting partner activities and achievements
- Engaging with relevant hashtags and discussions in the agroecology field
- Cross-promoting content with partner organizations

Following the RI-VIS style guide¹⁰ and guidelines, several content types will be produced during the different phases of the project:

a) User testimonials

- Format: short videos or quote graphics
- Details: researchers discussing their experience with AgroServ services
- Visual elements: photos of researchers in their work environment
- Tagging: involved entities and researchers
- Hashtags: #AgroServSuccess #AgroecologyResearch

b) Achievement stories

- Format: blog posts with accompanying social media teasers
- Details: highlighting specific project outcomes and AgroServ's role
- Visual elements: infographics summarizing key findings
- Links: full project reports or related scientific publications
- Hashtags: #Agroecology #SustainableAgriculture

c) Discussion prompts

- Format: poll questions or open-ended posts
- Details: thought-provoking questions about agroecology challenges
- Visual elements: custom graphics illustrating the question
- Hashtags: #AgroecologyDebate #FutureOfFarming

e) Expert commentary

- Format: responses to relevant industry news or research publications
- Details: AgroServ experts providing insights on current agroecology topics
- Tagging: Original content creators and relevant stakeholders
- Hashtags: #AgroecologyInsights

f) Service spotlights and Call announcements

¹⁰<https://toolkit.ri-vis.eu/>

1. Format: carousel posts, short videos, and infographics
2. Details: highlight specific services, explain application process
3. Visual elements: graphics illustrating service benefits, application timelines
4. Links: direct links to application pages
5. Hashtags: #AgroServCall #TransnationalResearch #ResearchOpportunity

Implementation strategy:

1. Develop a monthly content calendar balancing different content types
2. Ensure all content adheres to AgroServ brand guidelines
3. Monitor posts performance to refine strategy
4. Actively respond to comments and encourage discussions
5. Coordinate with consortium members for content creation and sharing

All social media activities will adhere to the brand guidelines outlined in section 4.1, ensuring a consistent visual identity across platforms. Active response to comments and discussion engagement, with a content calendar balancing the different content types will complement the implementation of the whole communication plan in the project's social media channels.

The Communications Officer will oversee the management of these digital platforms, coordinating with partners to gather content and ensure timely updates. The strategy will be flexible, allowing for adjustments based on analytics and emerging project needs.

4.2.3. Newsletters

AgroServ will produce and distribute quarterly external newsletters as a key component of our communication strategy. These newsletters will provide comprehensive updates on project activities and insights into agroecology.

Format: Email newsletter with web archive

Content sections:

1. Quarterly recap: summary of AgroServ's main activities and achievements over the past months
2. Agroecology focus: main editorial piece on a current topic related to agroecology
3. Consortium spotlight: Interview with a consortium partner, highlighting their role and contributions

4. Project news: updates on ongoing research, upcoming calls, and significant developments
5. Events: information on upcoming AgroServ events, webinars, and relevant conferences

Design elements:

- Visual elements: Infographics summarizing quarterly activities, photos of interviewed partners, event graphics
- Links: to full articles on the website, application pages for calls, and event registration
- Call-to-Action: encourage subscribers to share the newsletter and follow social media channels

Distribution strategy:

- Build and maintain a subscriber list through website sign-ups and event registrations
- Send newsletters at consistent times each quarter
- Share key newsletter content across social media platforms to increase reach
- Archive newsletters on the AgroServ website for easy access

The quarterly newsletter will complement the website and social media initiatives and actions , providing regular, in-depth updates to stakeholders while driving traffic to our online platforms and promoting engagement with our services and events.

4.3. Future communication materials

As the AgroServ project progresses, additional communication materials such as templates, presentations, leaflets, videos, and other visual aids will be developed as needed, and according to the Executive Committee and Management Board requirements. These materials will adhere to the brand guidelines outlined in Section 4.1 and will be designed to support the digital presence and content strategy described in Section 4.2. The development and implementation of these materials will be overseen by the Communications Officer, ensuring consistency and effectiveness across all project communications.

5. Implementation and Organization

5.1. Internal communication strategy

Effective internal communication is crucial for the success of the AgroServ project. The internal communication strategy aims to ensure smooth information flow, foster collaboration, and maintain alignment across all consortium partners.

Key components:

1. Communication Channels:

- Project management platform: NextCloud (cloud.agroserv.eu) serves as our primary collaboration tool for document sharing, task management, and internal discussions.
- Regular video conferences: monthly meetings will be held to discuss progress, challenges, and upcoming activities.
- Email: for formal communications and announcements, email will be used, with established mailing lists for different groups within and outside the consortium¹¹.

2. Information flow:

- Work Package (WP) leaders will provide monthly updates on their respective WPs during the Management Board meetings.
- The Project Manager will compile and distribute a quarterly internal newsletter summarising key developments across all WPs.
- A shared calendar will be maintained to track important deadlines, events, and milestones.

3. Knowledge sharing:

- Regular internal webinars will be organized for partners to present their work and share insights.

¹¹ As of October 2024 two main mailing lists are established, one internal (exclusive to consortium partners) and one external (open to audiences outside the consortium).

- A shared repository of best practices, lessons learned, and frequently asked questions will be maintained and regularly updated using the project's shared cloud space.
- An internal repository in the projects' cloud space will be established to document project processes and methodologies.

3. Onboarding process:

- A comprehensive onboarding package with communication materials and best practices will be developed for new team members joining the project.
- When needed, regular orientation sessions will be conducted to integrate new members into the project's communication practices.

By implementing this internal communication strategy, we aim to create a collaborative environment that supports the efficient execution of project activities and fosters a sense of shared purpose among all AgroServ partners.

5.2. Organization of external communication strategy

This section outlines the organizational structure and processes for implementing the external communication strategy detailed in sections 3 and 4.

1. Coordination structure:

- The Communication Officer will lead the implementation of the external communication strategy.
- The Communication Board will consist of representatives from each partner organization.
- The Board will meet monthly via video conference to discuss ongoing activities and upcoming plans.

2. Workflow for content creation and dissemination:

- A centralised content calendar will be maintained using a shared project management tool
- Partners will submit content ideas and materials through the Communication Board working document.
- The Communication Officer will review submissions within 5 working days.
- A two-tier approval process will be implemented:

- Tier 1 (Social media posts, blog articles, newsletters): approval by Communication Officer
- Tier 2 (Press releases, major announcements and long term content): approval by Communication Officer and the Executive Committee
- Approved content will be scheduled for dissemination using a social media management tool

6. Evaluation and Monitoring

Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)¹²

Evaluation reports to assess performance will be drafted. This will help the project re-evaluate the utility of certain communication choices. Some key performance indicators (KPIs) include:

Website	Time on site
	Page views per visit
	Number of unique connections
	Number of downloads
	Conversion and bounce rates
	New and returning visitors
	Traffic source & map of the origin of users (average)
Social media	Number of interactions, clicks, views, follows
	<i>Growth in follower count across platforms (LinkedIn, Twitter)</i>
	<i>Reach and impressions of posts</i>
Email newsletters	<i>Open rate</i>
	<i>Subscriber growth rate</i>
	<i>Click-through rate</i>
Events	Number of events
	Number of attendees per event (+gender balance)
Stakeholder engagement	<i>Number of applications received for open calls</i>
	<i>Number of new partnerships or collaborations initiated</i>
	<i>Diversity of stakeholders engaged (across different sectors and countries)</i>
Media coverage	<i>Number of media mentions</i>
	<i>Reach of publications featuring AgroServ</i>
	<i>Quality of coverage (sentiment analysis)</i>
Content performance	<i>Most viewed/downloaded content</i>
	<i>Engagement rates for different content formats (e.g., videos, infographics)</i>

Table 3: list of main KPIs

Other KPIs will be further investigated to evaluate and measure the results of the communication strategy.

¹² In italics are the KPIs that are an addition to the first version of this deliverable.

Appendix 1:

Event planning checklist

LOGISTICS	DEADLINE	DONE ON D/M	BY
Venue booking (auditorium, room, etc.)	As soon as possible		
Catering estimate (coffee-break, lunch, buffet, cocktail...)	1 month ahead		
Stewards estimate	1 month ahead		
Catering confirmation with the number of registered persons	D- 7		
Stewards confirmation	D-7		
Send the badges to print (+signage design for the venue)	D-7		
Work on orientation signage	D-3		
Send list of registrants to venue	D-3		
Meet with the technical staff and schedule a technical test with them inside the venue	D-3		
Send guest lists to reception desk / QRcode scan	D-3		
Send the programme to the venue	D-3		

INVITATIONS	DEADLINE	DONE ON DAY/MONTH	BY
Finalise the complete guest list	As soon as possible		
Create the registration form / site (File Survey or ScienceConf)			
Send a save the date message	2 months ahead		
Send the official invitation with the programme and the registration link	1 month ahead		
Send a reminder	D-15		
Extract the list of registrants	D-7		

COMMUNICATION	DEADLINE	DONE ON DAY/MONTH	BY
Build the event agenda/programme	As soon as possible		
Invite speakers	As soon as possible		
Finalise and validate the programme	1 month ahead		
Decide on goodies/books/booklets and check existing stock	1 month ahead		
Confirmation of speakers + sending of the final programme + request their ppt's	D-15		
Prepare a team schedule for the D-day	D-7		
Store all presentation on a flash drive	D-2		

POST- EVENT	DEADLINE	DONE ON DAY/MONTH	BY
Create a satisfaction form/survey (feedback & insights)			
Send a thank you note to speakers + collect missing ppt			
Upload the presentations to the shared cloud			
Send a thank you email to attendees with the form link + website link			
Assess participation (number of attendees, etc.)			
COM report			

Appendix 2:

Communicating about a scientific news

You are a researcher, and you have been granted access to the AgroServ services as part of your research? You are required to acknowledge the support of the AgroServ project (infrastructures & data).

Peer-reviewed communications

➤ **Your work has been selected to be:**

- published in a peer-reviewed journal,
- published in edited volumes, books, or reports,
- communicated during conferences or patent announcements, etc.

➤ **As soon as your publication is accepted, you must:**

- Notify the AgroServ communications officer and make sure to include them in the
 - exchanges from the early stages of drafting press releases and communication
 - supports, and this for coordination purposes.
- Share with them a summary in English following the recommendations listed below:

- 1. A title**, preferably "catchy", not exceeding one line.
- 2. A lead paragraph** ≈ 500 characters (including spaces), name of the journal/book, etc., context and issue addressed, approaches and results, elements of novelty and originality, perspectives opened, list of collaborations.
- 3. A text of about 1 page** developing the elements of the lead summary, "popularized" enough to be accessible to a wide audience, while remaining "scientific" without being too technical.
- 4. One or more illustrations** with a good resolution with credit and caption. This illustration can be a figure, an image, and/or a diagram, etc. For copyright reasons, these illustrations must be different from those used in the publication (except in the case where the scientific journal allows the free resharing of visuals, such as Nature Communications). Modifications (change of format / presentation / colour / orientation, etc...) are acceptable if they make these illustrations different from those of the article by several elements. You can also include *video images* made as part of your research.

5. **The reference of the publication in PubMed format.** It will be completed when the embargo is lifted. **You are a researcher, and you have been granted access to the AgroServ services as part of your research?** You are required to acknowledge the support of the AgroServ project (infrastructures & data) and EU funding.
6. **To which SDG does this research contribute and why?**
7. **Your contact details** including the name of the laboratory and the directors.
8. **The contact information of the communication correspondent of your laboratory/institution.**
9. **The Twitter/LinkedIn accounts** of the authors to be able to mention them.

Popular / General communications

- **Your work might be covered by the press or featured in the media**, etc.
- Inform the Communications Officer in advance to prepare a press release
 - As soon as the article or interview is published share with us the link and a news brief.

Important: all texts published on the AgroServ website must be validated by:

- the co-authors of the article
- the director of their unit
- the communication board of AgroServ.

Appendix 3:

Target audiences and planned actions

	Scientific community	Agricultural community	Policy makers & public bodies	Unions, associations & NGOs	Agriculture related industries	Research partners	Other projects & ERICs	General public	Press & media
Website (news, articles, feature stories, etc.)	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Social media	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
E-mail campaigns	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Conferences & events	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Printed materials	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Videos & infographics	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Face to face information	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Presentations	X	X	X	X	X	X	X		
Liaison with other initiatives	X	X	X	X	X	X	X		X
Press	X	X	X	X	X	X	X		X

Appendix 4:

GANTT of communication activities

Appendix 3 in the previous version of the deliverable has been removed, as a full list of partners is now available on the website of the project at this link: <https://agroserv.eu/about/our-european-partners>

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